

Potions!

Developed by: K20 Center

Article contributed by: Dave Carlgren

Keywords

Critical Thinking, Hypothesis Testing, Quantitative Reasoning, Science, Statistics

Figure 1. Gameplay screenshot from *Potions!* (K20 Center). Used for academic review and illustration. Rights remain with the original developer.

Introduction

Potions! (see Figure 1) is a puzzle game designed to improve understanding of hypothesis testing (K20 Center, n.d.). In this game, players attempt to blend different potions to save dying mythical creatures. Using one- and two-tailed tests with different potions, the player can see whether their concoction has an effect, is ineffective, or causes damage to the creatures in the test group before attempting to apply it to the entire population. This game should appeal to introductory statistics classes and students willing to explore concepts with

a playful spirit. Potions! has been created with hypothesis testing firmly in mind, and all controls and actions are designed to produce clear outcomes from the player's tests. The game has been developed by the K20 Center at the University of Oklahoma.

Facts

Release date:	2016
Developer:	K20 Center
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	1
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	1–1.5 hours
Languages:	English
Environment:	Online play
Material:	Instructor resources are available. In-game tutorial walks the player through the steps.
Price:	Free with registration

Resonance & Criticism

Building on ideas such as engagement, enjoyment, flow, and framing statistical problems in a fictional narrative, Potions! is a relatively light introduction to hypothesis testing without undue simplification of the concepts. Players who are interested in learning through play and engagement have found Potions! to be a creative and fun way to learn hypothesis testing. Students who were more used to traditional lecture formats learned an equal amount, as indicated by performance on summative assessments, but were unsatisfied with the experience, as indicated by subjective feedback.

The K20 website reports that their games will "impact over 12,000 students in 46 Oklahoma schools" in 2018. Broader data is not currently available.

Game Principle & Process

This game is set in a fictitious fantasy world where mythical creatures are being cursed. Your job is to use hypothesis testing to save as many creatures as possible in several different trials with different antidotes. Using one- and two-tailed testing, modifying sample sizes, and analyzing the results, players determine the best possible formulation to save creatures.

The in-game tutorial provides a walkthrough of all the features and the basics of hypothesis testing. Once the levels are entered, the game gets much more challenging as the data becomes harder to interpret based on the tests run.

The instructor guide clearly outlines the learning objectives, and the game remains true to these objectives.

The game uses a point system for each level: successfully saved creatures earn +3 points, while those who perish earn no points. Each level has a minimum score to pass and move to the next challenge. This is a single-player game with no player interaction.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Potions! is all about hypothesis testing in a fictional fantasy narrative structure. The game mechanics are simple and all directed toward helping the player reach the learning objectives. An in-class instructor may find it necessary to add explanations early in the game, but players also develop skills and interpretations rapidly as they play more. This game was designed to teach hypothesis testing, and it does so adequately and enjoyably, without sacrificing accuracy in mathematics or interpretation.

Effectiveness

No empirical evidence has been found to date on the effectiveness or learning impacts of Potions!

Potentially Problematic Aspects

The mythical creature narrative does an excellent job of eliminating sensitive topics. Younger players may find the inevitable death of test creatures to be challenging. As of this writing, Potions! is only available in English, and the reading level matches the topic.

An additional challenge is that the narrator occasionally uses jargon and slang in his written communications and instructions. The purpose of this is unclear, but it can be distracting at best and confusing at worst..

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

Sources

K20 Center. (n.d.). *K20 Game Portal: Games*. University of Oklahoma.
<https://games.k20center.ou.edu/games>